

Characterization and Modeling of Packet Loss of a VoIP Communication

L. Estrada, D. Torres, H. Toral

Abstract—In this work, a characterization and modeling of packet loss of a Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) communication is developed. The distributions of the number of consecutive received and lost packets (namely gap and burst) are modeled from the transition probabilities of two-state and four-state model. Measurements show that both models describe adequately the burst distribution, but the decay of gap distribution for non-homogeneous losses is better fit by the four-state model. The respective probabilities of transition between states for each model were estimated with a proposed algorithm from a set of monitored VoIP calls in order to obtain representative minimum, maximum and average values for both models.

Keywords—Packet loss, gap and burst distribution, Markov chain, VoIP measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN this work, modeling of a *Voice over Internet Protocol* (VoIP) communication through a wide area network (WAN) is developed and simulation based on this model is performed. The effects of correlated delay and loss in the sequence of packets on a voice communication are studied. And parameters of the proposed models are obtained from measurements of these VoIP calls.

Consecutive packet receipts and losses are named gaps and bursts, respectively[1]. Due to the time-correlated occupancy of the network, packet losses commonly occur in bursts. At small time scales, i.e., a few seconds or minutes, bursts occur with approximately the same distribution, and a two-state Markov chain can reproduce this phenomenon. Non-homogeneous bursty behavior becomes noticeable at larger scales and in this case the two-state Markov chain is insufficient, thus a more general model is necessary. The four-state Markov chain is applied then in order to capture (or simulate) the widely known bursty, non-homogeneous behavior of the characteristics of network traffic. This approach allows us to represent and simulate those periods with low and high loss rate that alternate in sequence according to certain probability.

The knowledge of the packet loss rate (PLR) and burst length distribution is useful to quantify the quality of the communication in the sense of certain metrics, e.g., mean opinion score (MOS).

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Statistical description of the four-state Markov chain, assuming time-homogeneity, is presented. Theoretical packet receipt and loss rates are quantified. Respective gap length and burst length (measured in number of packets lost/received) distributions are also described and a comparison, by means of the *square root of the mean squared error* (SMSE) of gap and burst length distributions, of two-state and four-state models is also performed.

II. MARKOV CHAINS

Let $S = S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m$ be the m states of an m -state Markov chain and let p_{ij} be the probability of the chain to pass from the state S_i to the state S_j , i.e., $p_{ij} = P(X_i = x_i | X_{i-1} = x_{i-1})$. Having the Markov property means that, given the present state, future states are independent of the past states, i.e., $P(X_{n+1} = x_{n+1} | X_n = x_n, X_{n-1} = x_{n-1}, \dots) = P(X_{n+1} = x_{n+1} | X_n = x_n)$. The Markov chains used in this work also are time-homogeneous, which means that the probabilities of transition between states are constant over time, i.e.,

$P(X_{n+1} = x_{n+1} | X_n = x_n) = P(X_n = x_n | X_{n-1} = x_{n-1})$. All states communicate (are reachable from) each other, which makes the chain irreducible. Also, the chain is aperiodic, i.e., state S_i can be reached from itself in any number of steps ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

The probabilities of transitions between states can be represented by a *transition matrix*. The elements of the one-step $m \times m$ transition matrix \underline{T} are $T_{ij} = p_{ij}$. To obtain the n -step transition matrix it is necessary to multiply the matrix itself n times[2], i.e.,

$$\underline{T}_n = \underline{T}^n. \quad (1)$$

As the number of steps (n) increases, the probability of transition to the state S_i depends less of the initial state. i.e., as n tends to ∞ , the matrix \underline{T}_n converges to a matrix with the next form:

$$\underline{T}_\infty = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \underline{T}_n = \begin{bmatrix} s_1 & s_2 & \dots & s_m \\ s_1 & s_2 & \dots & s_m \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s_1 & s_2 & \dots & s_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

such that

$$s_1 + s_2 + \dots + s_m = 1 \quad (3)$$

In (3), s_i represents the named *steady* probability of state S_i . The steady-state transition matrix T_∞ can be obtained then by solving (3) and (4) **Error! Reference source not found.]:**

$$[s_1 \ s_2 \ \dots \ s_m]T = [s_1 \ s_2 \ \dots \ s_m] \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the chain is irreducible and aperiodic, the Matrix T_∞ is defined and unique.

III. TWO- AND FOUR-STATE MODELS

The two-state Markov chain is shown in Fig. 1. State S_1 represents packet loss and S_2 , packet receipt. Two substitutions ($p_{11} = 1 - p_{12}$ and $p_{22} = 1 - p_{21}$) are made in order to represent the chain with the lowest number of parameters. The steady-state probability of the chain to be in the state S_1 , namely the packet loss rate, is given by (5) **Error! Reference source not found.]:**

$$s_1 = \frac{p_{21}}{p_{12} + p_{21}} \quad (5)$$

and clearly $s_2 = 1 - s_1$.

Fig. 1: Two-state Markov chain. White and shady circles represent correct and erroneous states, respectively.

The burst length and gap length distributions ($f_b(k)$ and $f_g(k)$, respectively) can be expressed in terms of p_{12} and p_{21} , as expressed by (6) and (7):

$$f_b(k) = p_{12}(1 - p_{12})^{k-1} \quad (6)$$

$$f_g(k) = p_{21}(1 - p_{21})^{k-1} \quad (7)$$

which have also respective averages $E\{f_b(k)\} = 1/p_{12}$ and $E\{f_g(k)\} = 1/p_{21}$. It is easy to proof (6), as $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_b(k) = 1$ and $f_b(k+1) = f_b(k) \cdot (1 - p_{12})$; and similarly for (7).

The four-state Markov chain is shown in Fig. 2. Missing arrows indicate zero probability. States S_1 and S_3 (shady circles) represent packet losses (erroneous); S_2 and S_4 (white circles), packet receipt (correct).

Six parameters ($p_{21}, p_{12}, p_{43}, p_{34}, p_{23}, p_{32} \in (0,1)$) are necessary to define all these probabilities. Without loss of generality, probabilities of transitions between correct states, as well as transitions between erroneous ones, have been assigned to zero.

Fig. 2: Four-state Markov chain. White and shady circles represent correct and erroneous states, respectively.

The four steady-state probabilities of this chain are:

$$s_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{p_{12}}{p_{21}} + \frac{p_{12} \cdot p_{23}}{p_{21} \cdot p_{32}} + \frac{p_{12} \cdot p_{23} \cdot p_{34}}{p_{21} \cdot p_{32} \cdot p_{43}}} \quad (8)$$

$$s_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{p_{21}}{p_{12}} + \frac{p_{23}}{p_{32}} + \frac{p_{23} \cdot p_{34}}{p_{32} \cdot p_{43}}} \quad (9)$$

$$s_3 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{p_{34}}{p_{43}} + \frac{p_{32}}{p_{23}} + \frac{p_{21} \cdot p_{32}}{p_{12} \cdot p_{23}}} \quad (10)$$

$$s_4 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{p_{43}}{p_{34}} + \frac{p_{32} \cdot p_{43}}{p_{23} \cdot p_{34}} + \frac{p_{21} \cdot p_{32} \cdot p_{43}}{p_{12} \cdot p_{23} \cdot p_{34}}} \quad (11)$$

The packet loss rate, i.e., the probability of the chain to be either in S_1 or in S_3 , is then:

$$r = s_1 + s_3 \quad (12)$$

The average burst length (\bar{b}) is calculated as the quotient of the probability of loss and the probability of transition from a lossless state to a loss state or vice versa (13). Let $t_{c \rightarrow e}$ and $t_{e \rightarrow c}$ be the respective number of transitions from correct states to error states and from error states to correct states. Their absolute difference ($|t_{c \rightarrow e} - t_{e \rightarrow c}|$) is at most 1 and it can be considered 0 as n tends to ∞ , i.e., the transitions from error state to correct state and vice versa have equal probability ($s_2(p_{21} + p_{23}) + s_4(p_{43}) = s_1(p_{12}) + s_3(p_{34} + p_{32})$) and then the average burst length (\bar{b}) is:

$$\bar{b} = \frac{s_1 + s_3}{s_2(p_{21} + p_{23}) + s_4(p_{43})} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, the average gap length is:

$$\bar{g} = \frac{s_2 + s_4}{s_2(p_{21} + p_{23}) + s_4(p_{43})} \quad (14)$$

The authors of **Error! Reference source not found.**] derived the gap length distribution for a two-state model, in which, as opposite to the two-state of Fig. 1, losses and receipts are allowed in the two states. The distribution of burst length of the four-state Markov chain of Fig. 2 is obtained, similarly as in **Error! Reference source not found.**], as follows:

Let $f_b(k)$ denote the probability that the burst length is k ; $C_1(k)$, the probability that the burst length is k or greater and the k^{th} transmission is from state S_1 and $C_3(b)$, the probability that the burst length is k or greater and k^{th} transmission is from state S_3 and $C_b(k)$, the probability that the burst length is k or greater such that $C_b(k) = C_1(k) + C_3(k)$ and $f_b(k) = C_b(k) - C_b(k+1)$. Clearly $C_b(k) = \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} f_b(i)$. Also, as transitions between states S_1 and S_3 have zero probability, $C_1(k+1) = C_1(k) \cdot (1 - p_{12}) = C_1(1) \cdot (1 - p_{12})^k$ and $C_3(k+1) = C_3(k) \cdot (1 - p_{34} - p_{32}) = C_3(1) \cdot (1 - p_{34} - p_{32})^k$. Then to calculate $f_b(k)$ it is necessary to obtain $C_1(1)$ and $C_3(1)$, whose respective values are $C_1(1) = s_2 \cdot p_{21} / [s_2(p_{21} + p_{23}) + s_4 \cdot p_{43}]$ and $C_3(1) = (s_2 \cdot p_{23} + s_4 \cdot p_{43}) / [s_2(p_{21} + p_{23}) + s_4 \cdot p_{43}]$

As the minimum burst length is 1, $C_b(1) = C_1(1) + C_3(1) = 1$. Then, the distribution of the burst length is:

$$f_b(k) = C_1(1) \cdot Q_1(k) + C_3(1) \cdot Q_3(k) \quad (15)$$

where $Q_1(k) = (1 - p_{12})^{k-1} - (1 - p_{12})^k = p_{12} \cdot (1 - p_{12})^{k-1}$ and $Q_3(k) = (1 - p_{34} - p_{32})^{k-1} - (1 - p_{34} - p_{32})^k = (p_{34} + p_{32}) \cdot (1 - p_{34} - p_{32})^{k-1}$. As expressed by (15), $f_b(k)$ is the sum of two geometric series with respective rates $1 - p_{12}$ and $1 - p_{34} - p_{32}$; this implies that $f_b(k)$ is a decreasing function of k , i.e., greater bursts have lower probabilities than shorter ones.

A similar procedure can be followed to obtain the gap length distribution ($f_g(k)$), which is:

$$f_g(k) = C_2(1) \cdot Q_2(k) + C_4(1) \cdot Q_4(k) \quad (16)$$

Where $C_2(1) = (s_1 \cdot p_{12} + s_3 \cdot p_{32}) / [s_1 \cdot p_{12} + s_3 \cdot (p_{32} + p_{34})]$, $C_4(1) = (s_3 \cdot p_{34}) / [s_1 \cdot p_{12} + s_3 \cdot (p_{32} + p_{34})]$, $Q_2(k) = (1 - p_{21} - p_{23})^{k-1} - (1 - p_{21} - p_{23})^k = (p_{21} + p_{23}) \cdot (1 - p_{21} - p_{23})^{k-1}$ and $Q_4(k) = (1 - p_{43})^{k-1} - (1 - p_{43})^k = p_{43} \cdot (1 - p_{43})^{k-1}$. Also note that $C_2(1) + C_4(1) = 1$.

IV. NUMERICAL APPROXIMATION OF THE MATRIX OF PROBABILITIES

Obtaining analytical expressions for the elements of T_{∞} (i.e., s_1, s_2, \dots) can be difficult when the number of states is large. In this case, a numerical approximation is more suitable, which is described as follows:

Let T be a $m \times m$ transition matrix, which has a unique

steady-state solution, and let $\{(\lambda_i, \bar{v}_i); i = 1, \dots, m\}$ be its pairs of eigenvalues and eigenvectors (i.e., $T\bar{v}_i = \lambda_i\bar{v}_i$), such that $\lambda_i > \lambda_j$ for $i < j$. This matrix T can be decomposed into the special form

$$T = PDP^{-1} \quad (17)$$

where P is a matrix composed of the eigenvectors of T , D is the diagonal matrix constructed from the corresponding eigenvalues and P^{-1} is the inverse of P . Then T_n can be calculated easily as

$$T_n = PD^nP^{-1} \quad (18)$$

As all elements of the diagonal of the matrix D are lower than 1 except $D_{1,1}$, then

$$T_{\infty} = PD^{\infty}P^{-1} = PD'P^{-1} \quad (19)$$

where the only non-zero element of D' is $D_{1,1} = 1$.

This method is also useful when obtaining short-term approximations, i.e., T_n for small n .

V. MODELING LOSS SEQUENCES

The traces studied in this work are those corresponding to Sets 3 and 4, described in **Error! Reference source not found.**] and **Error! Reference source not found.**]. There are 48 traces in total. Each one represents the packet receipt and loss of an 1-hour VoIP call.

An empirical algorithm is used to estimate the parameters of the Markov chain. For the two state Markov model let Y_t be the sequence that represent packet receipts and losses, i.e., $Y_t = 0$ if packet t was received and $Y_t = 1$ if it was lost. Packets are sent with a constant rate, e.g., a packet is sent each 20ms.

A. Two-state Case

In this case the values of p_{12} and p_{21} are estimated as follows: $p_{12} = t_{c \rightarrow e} / n_1$ and $p_{21} = t_{e \rightarrow c} / n_0$. Where $t_{c \rightarrow e}$ and $t_{e \rightarrow c}$ are the respective number of transitions from correct states to error states and from error states to correct states, and n_0 and n_1 are the respective number of received and lost packets.

B. Four-state Case:

In this case the values of the sequence Y_t are divided into regions of two types: the first with lower loss rate (whose first and last values are zeros) and the second with higher loss rate (whose first and last values are ones) than certain threshold, e.g., 1%. Then, from the first region, p_{12} and p_{21} are estimated the same way than in a two-state model. Similarly, p_{43} and p_{34} are estimated from the second region. Finally, let $t_{1st \rightarrow 2nd}$ be the number of transitions from the first region to the second; $t_{2nd \rightarrow 1st}$, the number of transitions from the second to the first; n_{1st} , the number of received packets in the first region (zeros) and n_{2nd} , the number of lost packets in the

second region (ones), then $p_{23} = t_{1st \rightarrow 2nd} / n_{1st}$ and $p_{32} = t_{2nd \rightarrow 1st} / n_{2nd}$. Also, the burst and gap histograms can be obtained from the sequence Y_t .

Fig. 3: Burst length distribution of a VoIP communication. Two-state and four-state models represent it adequately

Fig. 4: Gap length distribution of a VoIP communication. Four-state model fits better this distribution than two-state model

VI. COMPARISON OF TWO- AND FOUR-STATE MODELS

An example with one of the traces measured, obtained from a VoIP communication with codec G.711 and sampling time of 20ms, is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 5: PP-plot of the respective two-state and four-state burst histograms

In the traces under study it is found that, although the two-state model is adequate for the burst length distribution (see Fig. 5), the four-state model performs better when modeling the gap length distribution, as shown in Fig. 6. This is because the burst length distribution approaches rapidly to very low

values (near zero), but in the case of the gap length distribution, which presents slower decay, the two-state model does not fit the measured distribution due to its non-flexible one-parameter formula (see (7)).

For each trace that represents a loss sequence, the parameters of both two-state and four-state models are obtained.

The estimated statistics of the two-state and four-state transition probabilities are shown, respectively, in Table I and Table II.

Fig. 6: PP-plot of the respective two-state and four-state gap histograms

TABLE I
STATISTICS FOR TWO-STATE MODEL

	P_{21}	P_{12}
MIN	0.000322	0.595744
MAX	0.038605	0.934703
MEAN	0.013923	0.852838
STD. DEV.	0.012234	0.074697

TABLE II
STATISTICS FOR FOUR-STATE MODEL

	P_{21}	P_{12}	P_{43}	P_{34}	P_{23}	P_{32}
MIN	0.000188	0.963636	0.015503	0.096774	0.000016	0.000890
MAX	0.002053	1.000000	0.272727	0.931464	0.002551	0.361111
MEAN	0.000793	0.998997	0.054215	0.688747	0.000602	0.092536
STD. DEV.	0.000527	0.005424	0.037093	0.259845	0.000609	0.106315

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the SMSE between the burst length and gap length distributions and their respective two-state and four-state models. The four-state model fits the distribution better than two-state model for most traces. In cases where SMSE is large (e.g., greater than 0.001 for the four-state gap length distribution of Fig. 8) the packet loss is low (e.g., lower than 0.23%), then the gap length distribution cannot be adequately sampled, a larger number of samples is necessary in these cases. Note that each one of these traces represents an 1-hour call. In shorter periods, where non-bursty losses are present, these can be modeled adequately by two-state model.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, packet receipt and loss are modeled by discrete finite-state Markov chains. The packet loss rate, packet receipt rate and the distributions of burst length and gap length are described in terms of the Markov chain parameters, i.e., the

probabilities of transition between states. Algorithms for estimating the probabilities of transition for both two-state and four-state models, which are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, are presented.

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Fig. 7: SMSE of two-state and four-state burst histogram for all traces

Fig. 8: SMSE of two-state and four-state gap histogram for all traces

For modeling bursts and gaps of short communications, e.g. calls with a duration of a few minutes, the two-state model is sufficient; but for longer periods, the four-states model fits better. The performance of both models was evaluated by means of the SMSE of the burst length and gap length distributions, showing that although the two-state model fits adequately the burst length distribution, it cannot follow the slow decay of the gap length distribution of measurements.

The traces for which the SMSE of the four-state model was higher (e.g., greater than 0.001) had very low loss rates (less than 0.23%), so the gap length distribution was not adequately sampled.

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